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TEA TOURISM: AN EMERGING MARKET FOR INDIAN TOURISM INDUSTRY

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ABSTRACT

Tea tourism in India is fast catching on popularity with more and more tourists making their way to the lush green tea estates of India. Speaking of tea cultivation in India, it has been flourishing since the British colonial times when Robert Bruce chanced upon tea plants growing wild in the state of Assam that is famous as the birthplace of Indian tea. Today, India boasts of three major regions - Assam, Darjeeling and Nilgiris - that produce some of the finest teas in the world.

India is the largest producer of tea and contributes around 32% of the total global output. Therefore it is not surprising to note that tea tourism in India is indeed flourishing with the country busy inviting tourists to see for them how its favourite beverage makes its way to people's homes around the world.

Tea tours to India will not only take you around luxuriant plantations around the country but will also give you the perfect opportunity to know all about its history and commercial importance. Stay at luxurious tea bungalows, ensconced in the best of comforts, enjoy interacting with tea workers, and try your hand at plucking tea leaves, visit tea factories - all as part of tea tours in India.

Indian Tea tourism as they say is India's answer to what Europe calls wine tourism. So why don't you book a tour with India Profile today and see for yourself what is so unique about it. Just think, lush green tea plantations, a tranquil ambience and loads of old worldly charm - simply heaven!

Key words: Tea tourism, Assam, Darjeeling , Nilgiris, tea plants, TEESTA TEA.

INTRODUCTION

ABOUT TEA

Tea is an aromatic beverage commonly prepared by pouring hot or boiling water over cured leaves of the tea plant, "Camellia sinensis". After water, tea is the most widely consumed beverage in the world. It has a cooling, slightly bitter, and astringent flavour that many people enjoy.

Tea originated in China as a medicinal drink it was first introduced to Portuguese priests and merchants in China during the 16th century. Drinking tea became popular in Britain during the 17th century. The British introduced it to India, in order to compete with the Chinese monopoly on the product.

Tea contains L-Theanine, an amino acid whose consumption is mildly associated with a calm but alert and focused, relatively productive (alpha wave-dominant) mental state in humans. This mental state is also common to meditative practice

WHAT IS TEA TOURISM

The term 'tea tourism', in this context, includes a wide range of activities, and not just appreciating tea. The term refers to the whole experience of tourism in the midst of a tea garden or estate. It would include:

1. Staying in a heritage bungalow (many of the bungalows inside the tea gardens have existed from the colonial period, hence the heritage aspect gives an extra advantage), or at a home-stay in a tea resort or in a modern resort
2. Trekking in the natural beauty of a tea garden
3. Appreciating tea through undertaking tea-drinking and tea-tasting sessions
4. Experiencing the whole process of tea production, from watching, and even participating in, the plucking of tea leaves to the entire cycle of processing of tea in factories.
5. Related activities: Trekking along nature trails, witnessing local culture, patronizing local artisans

Tea tourism is such a wonderful and recreational commercial organization that can satisfy the taste of tourists' interest. Tea tourism provides tourists the opportunity to avail all information and experience related to tea. Tourists can spend time amidst natural beauty of tea gardens, enjoy nature walk and trekking. Rafting and golf are also to be found. Tourists stay at luxurious tea bungalows, ensconced in the best of comfort. They can enjoy interacting with tea workers, partake in tea leaves plucking and participate in cultural festivals.

Tea Tourism has emerged as a very recent niche in the world tourism scenario. It has parallels with food related tourism such as wine tourism of European countries like France, which has enjoyed wide acclaim and investigation by many researchers (Demhardt.2003). Tea tourism in India, like in China, Sri Lanka, Kenya, Malaysia and Taiwan, is catching fast on popularity recently and increasing number of tourists are rushing to the lush green tea estates of Darjeeling, the Nilgiris and Assam. Since 1990 some tea estates in India have started accommodating guests in their bungalows flagging off tea tourism. In the year 2000 with India market opening up for cheap international tea, the stiff competition has turned some tea estates open up their campus for overnight guests chiefly as a means of earning revenue through a side-line business opportunity.

THE HEALTHY EFFECTS OF GREEN TEA

Green tea, with its sweet aroma and eternally fresh taste has been approved and drunk since its introduction to Japan centuries ago. Modern research has finally put up why as a functional food Green tea is indispensable and should prove a popular beverage for the health conscious generation. It is indeed as researchers say "A miraculous medicine with an extraordinary power to prolong".

Green Tea has the following components:

Catechins - Reduces incidence of cancer, Reduces tumours, Reduces mutations, Reduces oxidation by active oxygen, Lowers blood cholesterol, Inhibits increase of blood pressure, increase of blood sugar, Kills bacteria, influenza virus, Fights carcinogenic bacteria, Prevents halitosis.

Caffeine - Acts as diuretics

Vitamin C - Reduces stress Prevents flu

Theanine (a kind of amino acid) - Gives green tea its delicious taste

Vitamin B Complex - Aids carbohydrate metabolism.

TEA PLUCKING TEA & CANCER

Researchers from the National Center for Toxicological Research in the United States demonstrated that the flavins and polyphenols significantly inhibited the growth of human pancreatic and prostate tumor cells.

Their research also indicated that tea could have a role to play in changing the genes involved in the process of causing cancer. Another study published in the International Journal of Cancer indicated that men who drink between 2 and 3 cups of tea per day might reduce their risk of developing prostate cancer by up to 30% compared to the non-tea drinkers.

TEA & CARDIAC AILMENTS

The natural oxidant properties of tea may help reduce the risk of developing heart disease. The polyphenols in tea have beneficial effect on two long established heart disease risk factors - High Cholesterol - High Blood Pressure.

Tea Leafs To quote Dr Simon Maxwell, Clinical Pharmacologist, Edinburgh University, "Dietary flavonoids may play in reducing the risk of circulatory diseases".

TEA & ORAL HEALTH

Tea is one of the few natural sources of fluoride and has been shown to have positive effect on preventing tooth decay and gum disease. Scientists believe that drinking tea improves oral health by helping prevent dental caries, by minimizing the possibility of dental plaques, the scale caused by mouth bacteria that leads to gum disease.

TEA TOURISM ACTIVITIES

Each nature beyond tea tour has various flavours depending on the places and on your requirement. Given below some ideas:

1. Accommodation in Tea Bungalow with garden fresh bio-organic food

2. Tea Garden Walk
3. Tea Processing observation
4. Tea Testing
5. Picnic day out with Birding or fishing
6. Interaction with the Garden workers
7. Ethnic cultural program with bon fire
8. Nature tours, forest safaris and excursions
9. Hill toy train ride (Darjeeling Himalayan Railways)
10. Miscellaneous entertainment with golf, tennis and indoor game

THE TEESTA TEA & TOURISM FESTIVAL

The Teesta Tea and Tourism Festival, celebrated in splendid manner in the tranquil serenity of the hills of Darjeeling. The Festival is celebrated in series at Darjeeling, the Dooars and in Sikkim with a motive of promoting tourism heritage of these places. The Teesta Tea and Tourism Festival in Darjeeling is jointly organized by the West Bengal Tourism, Darjeeling Gorkha Hill Council and Sikkim Tourism and supported by the Govt. of India Tourism along with the Private Tour Operators and Hotel owners.

Celebration

Teesta Tea & Tourism Festival is organized amidst the hilly areas of Darjeeling. Darjeeling is the beautiful place laden with the long stretch of tea gardens producing “champagne of the east” – Tea. The festival is celebrated in the grandiose manner and witnessed by large number of people including locals and tourists from distant places. This festival is full of excitement and fun filled activities like food carnival, film fest, toy-train ride, Water sports, visit to sanctuaries, nature walk etc. The calm hilly area attains the different dimension with wonderful colour and music of festivity. The festive aura of this occasion refreshes every one visiting this Teesta Tea & Tourism festival.

Time for celebration

The Teesta Tea & Tourism festival is one of the major festivals in the northern part of West Bengal and organized in the months of November December to attract large number of tourists.

TATA TEA MUSEUM

The Tata Tea Museum in the Nallathanni Estate tells the eventful story of Munnar; its transformation from an uninhabited stretch of forest land to a plantation town. The highlights of the museum include old machineries used for tea processing, photographs and some other curious displays that throw light on the efforts of some adventurous planters who dared to conquer the wild with minimal equipment and little resource.

Rotorvane, an old tea roller used in the CTC type tea processing, would be a wonder for even those associated with modern tea industry. There is a CTC tea manufacturing unit in the museum where visitors can get to know the old method of tea processing. However, the real treat here would be the tea tasting unit where one can savour a variety of flavours.

And if you think that the displays are confined to just tea-making, you're wrong. Like the 'Pelton Wheel', used at a power generation plant set up at the Kanniamallay Estate in 1920s, a variety of exhibits show the infrastructure development activities which have happened in Munnar in its journey towards

becoming a major tea producing centre in the country.

Another proud display of the museum is a large sundial made in 1913, placed on a granite block, the sundial was made by Art Industrial School; Nazareth Tamil Nadu. There is also a section featuring classic furniture belonging to colonial bungalows. The exhibits include wooden chairs, tables, decorative displays, magneto phone, iron ovens and a wooden bath tub. Office furniture of tea estates like typewriters, manual calculators and an EPABX Dating from 1909 is also exhibited.

A burial urn discovered from the Periakanal tea estate in Munnar is also displayed at the museum. The urn dates back to second century BC. The museum is open from 10.00 a.m. to 5.00 p.m. on all days. Travellers are advised to contact the museum authorities prior to the visit.

THE INDIAN TEA ASSOCIATION –PROMOTE TEA TOURISM

Founded in 1881, the Indian Tea Association is the premier and the oldest organization of tea producers in India. The Association has played a multi-dimensional role towards formulating policies and initiating action towards the development and growth of the Industry, liaising with the Tea Board, Government and other related bodies. The ITA has branches at different locations in Assam and West Bengal. With over 425 member gardens, the ITA and its branches represent over 60% of India's total tea production. As employers, ITA member gardens provide direct employment to more than 400,000 people.

TEA GROWING REGIONS IN INDIA

Assam

Assam Tea, which has a rich history of satisfying its world admirers with its unique taste and flavour, has a rich heritage too which can equally satisfy the tourist community whether domestic or international. Assam Tea and the tea estates of Assam have many tourism aspects which the world community has already started to witness and cherish. Tea gardens of Assam with their lush greenery, the so called 'green carpet' with rows and rows of shade trees, the tea estate bungalows standing as relics of British colonial heritage, the tanned ethnic people with their distinct rhythmic music and dance carry potentialities to attract both domestic and international tourist interests and can present a magnificent revenue opportunity to the state.

Historically, Assam is the second commercial tea production region in world after southern China. Assam along with southern China is the only region in the world with native tea plants and 'Assam is the only region in the world where tea is grown in plains' (TBI). There is evidence of tea cultivation in Assam even before Major Robert Bruce is regarded to have discovered 'wild' tea bushes in Assam forests in 1823. In 1823, notable Assamese Maniram Dewan, listening to Robert Bruce discussing Chinese tea with a group of English merchants in Calcutta, approached and informed him that such a plant is cultivated in Assam by Singpho tribes (TBI). Maniram put Bruce in touch of Beesa Gam, a Singpho chief with whom Bruce came in an agreement to supply the plant and its seed against money (Baruah 2011). Later in 1834, Robert Bruce's brother Charles A. Bruce got it confirmed that the leaves that the Singpho tribe brewed and drank is a different variety of tea and tasted almost like Chinese tea when dried (TBI).

Tea-testing Assam variety of tea, which is referred to as Assam Tea is scientifically called *Camellia Sinensis* var. *Assamica*. Its unique feature is its body, briskness, malty flavour and strong bright colour. Assam tea and blends containing Assam tea are often sold as 'breakfast tea'. India, after being the largest tea producer of world for nearly hundred years has been very recently surpassed by China. Assam alone produces 16% of total world production which contributes to 54% of Indian tea production (TBI). Assam has 830 big tea estates with 529 estate tea factories mostly producing black tea. Assam tea is identified with the logo depicting a one horned rhinoceros. Assam orthodox tea is now a registered GI (Geographical Indication).

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There are various new ways and areas where the tea tourism can be flourishing with great extent. Some of these ways are mentioned below.

1. Bungalow culture

Tea estate bungalows of Assam carry a rich heritage being the relics of British colonial era. The Bungalow culture that the planters created in Assam in the 19th Century has its unique identity. The bungalows of Assam tea gardens have a signature style with its raised wooden platform (Chang Bungalow), spacious surrounding verandas, a low house having one or two stories, a fire place with a visible chimney, a

spacious yard with arrays of flowers plants and trees located in the midst of natural surroundings. The planters, most of whom were English, Scottish and Irish in those days, tried to create a small world of their dream, using local architecture and material. Some of these types of bungalows are like Hunlal Tea Estate Bungalow, Thengal Manor in Jorhat, Mistry Sahib's Bungalow of Gotoonga Tea Estate, Sangsua Tea Estate's Burra Shib Bungalow, Bungalows of Balipara, Charduar and Basha Tea Estate etc.

2. Organic Tea Estates

Organic Tea has recently become a matter of concern to the health conscious community of the world. From last few years many planters of Assam have started practicing organic methods of tea cultivation and production. Health conscious tourists, from across the country and abroad, have started to visit these plantation sites to see the manufacturing procedure personally and interact with the planters, adding a new chapter to the tea tourism of the region. Few names can be taken in this regard-

(A) SingphoTea

(b) Madhupur Village Tea etc.

3. Tocklai

Tea Research Centre- The Tea Research Centre at Tocklai has international tourist potential being a century old tea research institute, 'the only one of its kind in the world'(Bedi 2012). It may be a centre of interest for students and research fellow from any place with tea interest.

4. Tea Tribe Culture

The tea tribe of Assam, an admixture of communities transported from various places of Bihar, West Bengal, Orissa, Andhra Pradesh, Madhya Pradesh, Tamil Nadu and Chota Nagpur region of Jharkhand, and their tribal cultures may be of research interest and attract tourists. Tea laborers, although have been made to adjust themselves with industrial discipline, they have retained their rural character till date which can matter of interest of sociologists and anthropologists. Tribal rhythmic dance forms and their music may enthrall any tourist of any place and age.

Tourism has occupied a significant position in the economy of a country of present era as an industry earning foreign currency and strengthening national economy. Development of tea tourism in Assam, besides sustaining the environment and preserving the heritage and culture, will benefit the state by creating employment opportunities and boosting rural economy and thereby alleviate the insurgency and other socio-economic problems. If the Tea Tourism is highlighted with proper planning and proper prospects, it can help the Govt. to earn much revenue and also create a new shape of the state like Assam in the map of the world tourism sector.

Darjeeling

Total area under tea: 17,820 ha

Production: 9.8 million kg

Elevation: 90-1,750 metres

Rainfall: 3,000 -3,300 mm

Nestling in the foothills of the snow-covered Himalayan range, Darjeeling grows one of the world's most exclusive teas at altitudes ranging from 600 to 2,000 meters. A cup of Darjeeling is golden or amber in colour and has a unique, delicate flavour that is referred to as "muscatel," or, having the flavour of muscatel grapes, the typical flavour can also be described as "flowery," and sometimes, "peachy." So

delicate and tasty is the flavour that drinkers usually skip the milk and sugar often added to the bitterer, heavier black teas. Darjeeling connoisseurs literally cringe at the thought of adulteration.

Dooars and Terai

Total area under tea: 97,280 ha

Production: 216 million kg

Elevation: 90 -1,750 metres

Rainfall: 3,500 mm

By 1874. There were 113 tea gardens in Darjeeling district alone. This inspired planters to try out tea cultivation in the Terai region. James White set up the first Terai plantation called Champita in 1862. Planting was then extended to the Dooars. But the Assamese tea bush proved more suited to this region, Gazaldubi was the first Dooars garden, and by 1876 the area boasted 13 plantations, which in 1877 led the British to set up the Dooars Tea Planters' Association.

The Dooars and Terai gardens account for an annual production of 226 million kg, or over a quarter of India's total tea crop, with September considered an important month. The TAI has 48 member gardens in the belt.

Dooars

Lying in the Himalayan foothills, the Dooars have great natural beauty. Wildlife-rich tropical forests, innumerable hill streams cutting across the green carpet of tea gardens, undulating plains and low hills rising up from the rivers. The name Dooars is derived from 'doors' as the region is the gateway to the northeast of India and Bhutan. Dooars is also the gateway to the hill station of Darjeeling and the Sikkim region and is famous for its tea gardens, planted by the British.

The elevation of the Dooars area ranges from 90 m to 1750 m. There are innumerable streams and rivers flowing through these fertile plains from the mountains of Bhutan. Average rainfall of the area is about 3,500 mm. Monsoon generally starts from the middle of May and continues until the end of September. Winters are cold with foggy mornings and nights. Summer is mild and constitutes a very short period of the year. The economy of Dooars is based on the three Ts Tea, Tourism and Timber. Thousands of people are engaged as labourers in the tea estates and factories.

Kangra

Total area under tea: 2,348 ha

Production: 0.8 million kg

Elevation: 700-1,000 metres

Rainfall: 2,300-2,500 mm

In Himachal Pradesh, tea is grown in the Mandi and Kangra districts over an area of 2,063 hectares. Kangra, known as "the valley of gods," is famous for its distinct flavoured tea. Below the towering and exquisitely beautiful snow-clad Dhauladhar Mountain, tea has been grown on the gentle slopes of the outer Himalayas since 1949.

In 1849, Dr. Jameson conducted a feasibility survey of the valley of Kangra in Himachal Pradesh and found it suitable for tea cultivation. He brought China tea plants from the nurseries at Almora and Dehradun and planted them in Government gardens at Kangra, Nagrota and Bhawama. Despite having

suffered a good deal during transit, the plants grew well indeed. This encouraged the government to go ahead and establish the tea industry in the valley.

The Kangra tea industry occupied prime position with respect to its quality from the last quarter of the 19th century until date. Both black and green teas are manufactured in the Kangra valley. The predominating black teas were Pekoe, Pekoe Suchong, Coarse teas and Fannings, while among green teas, Hyson, Young Hyson and Coarse grades were the most popular ones.

Nilgiri

Total area under tea: 66,175 ha

Production: 135 million kg

Elevation: 1,000-2,634 metres

Rainfall: 1,000-1,500 mm

Nilgiri Tea, one of India's most distinctive teas, has been named after the Nilgiris or Blue Mountains where it is grown. The range is called the Blue Mountains because of the saxe-blue Kutinji flower which covers the hills when it blooms once in 12 years. Situated in South India, this picturesque range of undulating hills has tea growing at elevations ranging from 1,000 meters to 2,500 meters. Rainfall varies from 60 inches to 90 inches annually. These conditions favour the fine, elegant flavour and brisk liquor of Nilgiri teas. The combination of fragrance and briskness makes Nilgiri a truly unique tea, the likes of which cannot be found anywhere else in the world. If you like a fragrant tea with good body and superlative flavour. Nilgiri should be the one for you.

History

The Nilgiris was originally a summer retreat for the Europeans. John Sullivan, who built Stone House, his home in Ooty in 1823, was followed by several other Europeans. Later, when the Duke of Buckingham was Governor of Madras he started the practice of moving the government to the hills for the summer.

Tea was planted on an experimental farm in the Ketti Valley in 1853, but the first full scale efforts to plant tea in the Nilgiris were on Thiashola and Dunsandle Estates in 1859. In 1969, Glenmorgan became the first estate in South India to produce Green tea. Nilgiri tea now accounts for about 92 million kg per year, which is about 10% of the total tea production of India.

Afull-Hedged training centre set up with support from the Tea Board of India has been conducting regular training courses for planters with large gardens as well as small growers, on the modern aspects of crop husbandry and tea manufacture.

Tea attributes

A deliciously fragrant and exquisitely aromatic tea, with high tones of delicate floral notes and golden yellow liquor. Crisply brisk and bright. Lingering notes of dusk flowers with an undercurrent of briskness. Creamy mouth feel. A truly flavourful tea for a stressful day. Nilgiri Orthodox tea has recently been registered as a Geographical Indication in India.

Anamallais

Total area under tea: 12,625 ha

Production: 30 million kg

Elevation: 900-1,600 metres

Rainfall: 3,000-3,800 mm

Spanning an area of 389 sq km of magnificent hills ranging from 900 to 1,600 metres, the Anamallais are wedged between Tamil Nadu and Kerala and just across the hills from the High Ranges. With over 12,000 hectares under tea, it occupies an important place in the planting map of South India. The Tea Research Foundation, the second largest tea research institute managed by UPASI, is situated in the Anamallais.

History

Up to the middle of the 19th Century, this area was dense evergreen tropical rainforest with trees towering up to heights of 35 metres, with very little undergrowth. Two early pioneers, Carvesh Marsh and C.R.T Congreve, came to the district in 1857 and put up a camp at Paralai, where they planted coffee. It was only by 1908 that tea was planted at Paralai, where the pioneers had planted coffee more than half a century ago

The tribe of the 'Kaders' live on the periphery of the tea plantations. Their only contact with the early planters was as 'indifferent guides through the jungle, clearing the undergrowth". The original plantations were permitted subject to the Kaders being at liberty to enter the earmarked lands and to collect minor produce from it.

Tea attributes

Medium to high tone fragrance. Biscuity to floral notes. Lingering, biscuity aroma. Golden saffron liquor. Brisk and fairly bright. Strong and vibrant, complex and intense. Long finish of briskness. A great tea to provide the punch and verve to start the day. A Morning refresher!

Wayanad

Total area under tea: 5470 ha

Production: 16 million kg

Elevation: 850-1,400 metres

Rainfall: 2,000-2,500 mm

The evergreen forests of the Wayanad-Nilgiris range in Kerala and Tamil Nadu mark the transition zone between the northern and the southern eco-regions of the Western Ghats. This is a quiet place where scenic beauty, wildlife and traditions matter; where simplicity is a virtue.

Located a distance of about 76 km from the sea shore of Calicut, the area is full of plantations, forests and wildlife. The Wayanad hills are contiguous to the Mudumalai Wildlife Sanctuary and National Park in Tamil Nadu and the Bandhipur National Park in Karnataka, thus forming a vast mass of land where wild life moves about freely.

History

The earliest plantations in this area date back to 1845. When coffee was planted here. It was not until 1874 that tea was planted beginning with a few acres at New Hope estate in Ouchterlony Valley.

In the early 1880s, speculating that there was gold in Wayanad, many companies bought up the existing coffee and tea plantations in Cherambadi, Devala and Pundalur. Many mining companies sprouted up in the Wayanad, but they were all financial disasters for the investors.

By 1897 the 'gold bubble' had burst. With coffee having been wiped out by the stem borers and leaf diseases and the dream of gold having died its natural death, planters turned to tea and in 1897 tea planting commenced on Wentworth estate, the property of the erstwhile Wentworth Gold mining Company. Others soon followed and the district became largely a tea area.

Tea Attributes

Clean fragrance. Medium toned. Biscuit notes. Earthy reddish liquor. Mild and mellow, Full bodied with light briskness. A born soother.

Karnataka

Total area under tea: 2140 ha

Production: 6 million kg

Elevation: 750-1,000 metres

Rainfall: 2,000-3,500 mm

Chikmagalur is a famous coffee town of the Karnataka region of India about 150 miles from Bangalore. The plantations are located at a height of over 5000 feet. Nestled in the Baba Budan hills of the Sahyadris range, Chikmagalur around which most of the tea in Karnataka grows is a calm, serene town full of scenic surprises. The town enjoys a salubrious climate and is famous for its sprawling tea and coffee estates.

History

Indian coffee has its roots in Chikmagalur. It is believed that Baba Budan (earlier known as Hazrat Jamal) brought the first coffee seeds from Yemen to India. Coffee plantations in Karnataka State date back to 1841 when Thomas Canon planted coffee at Belur. Others followed suit and in spite of coffee's travails in later years the region continued with it and Karnataka is today the largest producer of coffee in India. Although coffee is king here, this region produces over 5 million kg of tea as well.

Tea Attributes

Simple and fragrant teas from Karnataka Golden ochre liquor Fair bodied and fairly brisk. Uncomplicated Balanced Medium toned. Short and simple finish. A tea you could drink cup after cup of, throughout the day.

Munnar - High Ranges

Total area under tea: 13,000 ha

Production: 27 million kg

Elevation: 950-2,600 metres

Rainfall: 1,300-7,000 mm

Munnar, the commercial centre of some of the highest tea growing estates in the world, is breathtakingly beautiful; a haven of peace and tranquility and an idyllic tourist destination in Kerala, India's most popular tourist destination. Set at an altitude of 6,000 feet in Idukki district, Munnar was the favoured summer resort of the erstwhile British rulers in the colonial days. Unending expanses of tea plantations, pristine valleys, mountains and waterfalls, exotic species of flora and fauna in its wild sanctuaries and forests and the aroma of spice scented cool air Munnar has all these and more.

History

Tea plantations in Munnar were started in the 1870s by A.M. Sharp, a European at the A.H. Sharp Parvathy estate (now known as the Silent Valley Estate). In 1895 Finlay, a European company, entered the scene and acquired about 33 tea estates in Munnar. In 1897 the Kannan Devan Hills Produce Company was formed to manage Finlay's estates. In 1964, The Tata Group, an Indian corporate giant, entered into a collaborative venture with Finlay leading to the formation of the Tata-Finlay group. In April 2005 tea plantations under the Tata group were transferred to a new company called Kannan Devan Hills Produce Co, Pvt Ltd, Today and the company manages 16 estates spread over about 8,600 hectares of land.

Tea Attributes

Clean and medium toned fragrance of sweet biscuit in a dip malt. Liquor of golden yellow with an orange depth and a rounded cup. Strong bodied with lively briskness, a touch of fruit and a startlingly lingering note of sweetness in the finish. Expect the unexpected. The beauty of the hills beckons you to an inspiring morning of tea. A lot can certainly happen over this cup of tea!

Travancore

Total area under tea: - 14,000 ha

Production: - 20 million kg

Elevation: - 750-1,350 metres

Rainfall: - 2,000-6,000 mm

Ascentic, high altitude area consisting of Peermade (which lies 85 km east of Kottayam), Vagamon, Thekkady and Vandiperiyar through which the River Periyar flows, enjoys a salubrious climate all-round the year. The area is surrounded by lush green plantations of tea, coffee, coconut, pepper, cardamom, rubber and eucalyptus and houses one of India's largest wildlife sanctuaries. It was once the summer retreat of the Maharaja of Travancore, who had two palaces here.

History

In 1802 J. D. Monro opened a coffee clearing on Mope Estate, now a part of Stag brook Estate and was followed almost immediately by Robert Baker on Stag brook and F.G Richardson on Twyford.

Although tea was tried out as an experiment just two years later, it was not until 1875, when the leaf disease appeared and spread rapidly, that the proprietors of coffee estates in the area began planting tea. This progressed rapidly and by 1906, there were 8,000 acres under tea, while those under coffee had come down to 500 acres.

Tea Attributes

Medium fragrance. Reddish liquor with dancing hues of yellow. A fairly balanced tea with body and briskness. Good for the evenings and as your evening companion

GOVERNMENT TO PROMOTE TEA TASTING TOURISM

If Europe has wine-tasting tourism, India's answer to that is a tea-testing tourist circuit. That, along with holding international conferences, is the new area India plans to focus on as it seeks to boost in-bound tourism in the coming years -Tourism and Culture Minister -Ambika Soni (Former Tourism Minister). There are plans to develop tea-tasting circuits similar to the wine-tasting tours offered in Europe,

At present, India's share is only about eight per cent of the annual global business of US dollars 280 million generated by convention tourism. Outlining the measures taken by the government and the industry to promote tourism sector, Soni said hotel capacity will be significantly improved with the addition of 100,000 new beds planned for the current year. Liberalisation of aviation sector and 100 per cent foreign investments allowed in tourism sector are expected to attract more foreign investments into the country, she said. Current efforts to diversify tourist attractions by offering new products such as adventure tourism, wellness tourism, medical tourism and golf tourism will have a positive effect on foreign tourist arrivals as well as on domestic tourism.

India's tourism promotion campaign as the "Partner Nation" at the International Tourism Exchange in Berlin has helped to generate a strong interest in the country's tourism offers among the trade visitors from around the world as well as among the German public. India's ITB promotion is significant not only because it comes as the country marks the 60th anniversary of its independence but it also recognises India's increasing prominence on the world tourism stage. Even though tourism growth in India has not been staggering and the 4.5 million tourist arrivals recorded in 2006 were only a tiny proportion of the 842 million arrivals world-wide, the outlook is very positive for achieving higher growth in the coming years.

The importance of tourism for Indian economy is evident from the fact that it contributed to 5.9 per cent of the Gross Domestic Product and provided employment to 41.8 million people. The year 2006 was not only a record year for India's inbound tourism but was the fourth year showing a double-digit increase in arrivals.

CONCLUSION

The evaluative study carried out so far on tea tourism sector in Assam portrays a clear picture about the state of affairs in terms of performance and its different stages of growth and development. Tea tourism though relatively new in concept has tremendous potentiality. A proper checked out design and plan to entire tourist is the need of the hour. That's why, it's a time to rethink, plan, manage and then act. "Even a five thousand mile journey must start with the first step", quotes an old Chinese proverb. It is yet again right saying that "One will have to go out and sell, instead of waiting for customers to come and buy" in a market 247 stiff competition. As such, a beginning has to be made soon, and together we could envisage in ushering in a new tea tourism era not only for the untouched eastern paradise of India, but the entire country as a whole.

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